

Machine Learning for Ukraine's Forest Cover Damage Assessment based on Satellite Data

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Abstract—This research presents a comprehensive machine learning approach for assessing forest cover damage in Ukraine based on satellite data from 2016 to 2024. Using Sentinel-1 and Sentinel-2 imagery processed through Google Earth Engine (GEE), we developed a Random Forest classification model to generate annual land cover maps with 10-meter spatial resolution. Our analysis reveals significant forest losses across Ukraine, totaling 190 thousand hectares by 2024 compared to 65 thousand hectares in 2021 (relative to 2016). The most substantial forest cover damage occurred within protected areas of the Emerald Network, particularly in eastern and southern regions affected by military operations. This research provides critical insights into the environmental impact of conflict on Ukraine's forest ecosystems and establishes a methodology for ongoing monitoring of these valuable natural resources.

Keywords—machine learning; satellite data; random forest; Emerald Network; forest loss.

I. INTRODUCTION

Ukraine's forest ecosystems are of great ecological, economic and social importance to the country [1]-[4]. Over the past decades, Ukrainian forests have undergone significant changes under the influence of a variety of factors, including climate change [5]-[10], economic

Figure 1. Examples of six locations with significant forest cover changes during 2016-2024 within Emerald Network

activity [11], natural disturbances [12] and, starting from 2014 and 2022, military operations [13]-[17]. A lot of studies are devoted to monitoring and analyzing the dynamics of forest changes in Ukraine, with a special emphasis on the period after the start of a full-scale invasion. In particular, the study [15] analyzes changes in the east of the country within the Emerald Network [20] from 1996 to 2020, in the study [14] assessed the dynamics of forest change for three locations after the start of a full-scale invasion (2022). Our work is devoted to the analysis of forest cover losses for the entire country, including the Emerald Network, as of 2024.

II. TERRITORY OF INTEREST AND DATA USED

A. Pilot Territory

Ukraine was chosen as the area of interest. A more detailed study was conducted within the protected areas of the Emerald Network of Ukraine. The greatest attention has been paid to six zones, due to the rather large dynamics of changes in forest cover area, especially during a full-scale war from 2022: 1) Siverskyi Donets river valley in Luhansk oblast; 2) Kreminski Lisy; 3) Siverskyi Donets river valley in Kharkiv oblast; 4) Ovrutskyi; 5) Korostyshivskyi; 6) Oleshkivski Pisky & Kinburnska Kosa. Fig. 1 shows the Emerald Network area for all of Ukraine (marked in light green), as well as six pilot sites where more detailed monitoring of forest cover changes is being conducted (marked in bright blue).

B. In-situ Data

To create forest maps, ground data collected along roads across Ukraine in 2016-2024 were used according to the JECAM guidelines [21], [22] using Avenza software. For the territories that were close to the war zone during these years, the image interpretation method [23] was used, where experts determined the types of land cover, including forests. For 2022 and 2024, for the territory of Ukraine, to obtain maps of forest types, data along roads on forest types (coniferous, deciduous and mixed) were used within the framework of the SWIFTT project, as well as the open data set LUCAS Copernicus 2022 [24], [25].

Table 1 presents the datasets by year for the territory of Ukraine that were used to construct and validate forest maps.

C. Satellite Data

Our classification approach necessitates Sentinel-1 composites spanning Ukraine's entire territory. We use Sentinel-1 data from descending orbits. For each 12-day interval between March 1 and September 1, we generate mean composites that typically blend overlapping scenes from neighboring orbits. We apply a neighborhood mean filter with kernel 3 to minimize speckle noise in these composites.

For Sentinel-2, we create nationwide composites based on Level-2A collection with a per-scene cloud threshold of 40%. Composite periods are selected to ensure cloud-free, gap-free imagery. Each granule undergoes cloud masking based on the SCL band, removing Cloud Shadows and Clouds, Cirrus, and Snow/Ice [26], [27]. The composite combines available images within the selected timeframe, calculating median values for pixels covered by multiple dates. We employ four 10m resolution spectral bands (B2, B3, B4, B8), omitting lower-resolution bands to optimize computational resources.

Before 2020 we have used Google Earth Engine Cloud platform [28] for satellite data processing and classification tasks. After this we have used the Copernicus Data Space Ecosystem (CDSE) platform [29] with satellite data processing showed on the Fig. 2.

Figure 2. Satellite data processing scheme for CDSE platform

While creating country-wide optical composites reduces informative data, this approach enables us to employ a complete training dataset simultaneously, developing a single model for the entire region and generating maps for areas with restricted ground data access (such as occupation zones or frontline areas).

III. METHODOLOGY

The GEE and CDSE platforms stand as a leading solution for extensive land cover classification tasks. Our research group has created a comprehensive LC/LU classification framework for expansive regions utilizing the GEE cloud environment, extending work from earlier studies [30], [31].

To address GEE resource limitations, we use centroids with 3-meter buffers from training polygon data rather than entire polygons. These centroids function as labeled points that efficiently train the classification model.

For classifier training, all Sentinel-1 and Sentinel-2 composites [32] are stacked with training data, employing the Random Forest algorithm - among GEE's most effective options. The output is a .tif classification map covering all of Ukraine, saved directly to the user's Google Drive.

IV. RESULTS

As a result of the work, 9 maps of land cover classifications from 2016 to 2024 for Ukraine with 10-meters spatial resolution were obtained, which made it possible to analyze the dynamics of forest cover changes. Annual maps of forest cover loss were obtained, as well as a long-term map of forest losses from 2016 to 2024. The F1-score for forest class score for all years is higher than 95%.

Figure 3. Forest cover loss in 2024 as a percentage of 2016

Figure 4. Forest losses 2016 - 2024 for Emerald Network, th. ha

TABLE I. TRAIN AND TEST POLYGONS FOR LAND COVER CLASSIFICATION

Year	2016	2017	2018	2019	2020	2021	2022	2023	2024
Cropland	6042	3733	6477	8673	9859	10214	5946	4766	8425
Artificial	135	135	328	445	481	545	567	698	714
Forest	676	683	1331	447	588	815	1012	934	972
Grassland	798	544	1301	1754	1922	2065	2067	1770	1920
Bare land	114	108	161	250	260	243	241	292	306
Water	176	192	480	678	690	738	740	768	783
Wetland	48	70	132	221	252	361	363	433	443
Damaged forest	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	254	303
Uncultivated land	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	254	310
Total	7989	5465	10210	12468	14052	14981	10936	10169	14176

Figure 5. Examples of six locations with significant forest cover changes during 2016-2024 within Emerald Network

Fig. 3 shows a map of forest cover loss as of 2024 as a percentage of the forest area in 2016 at oblasts level. The main losses are observed in the eastern and in the zone of active hostilities.

Fig. 4 shows the forest cover loss within the Emerald Network from 2016 to 2024. Red color saturation corresponds to larger losses. The total area of forest cover loss across Ukraine as of 2024 is 190 th. ha, compared to 65 th. ha of 2021.

The most significant and rapid changes occurred in the Siverskyi Donets river valley in Luhansk oblast (forest loss of 30.2 th. ha, Fig. 5.1), Kremynski Lisyy (7.5 th. ha, Fig. 5.2), Siverskyi Donets river valley in Kharkiv oblast (9.9 th. ha, Fig. 5.3), Ovrutskyi (7.7 th. ha, Fig. 5.4), Korostyshivskyi (1.44 th. ha, Fig. 5.5), Kinburnska Kosa (6.3 th. ha,) and Oleshkivski Pisky (5.7 th. ha) - Fig. 5.6. For better understanding, Fig. 5.1 and 5.2 also show examples of Sentinel-2 satellite data for the corresponding areas for 2016 and 2024, where changes in forest cover are clearly visible.

V. CONCLUSIONS

This study presents a robust framework for monitoring forest cover changes across Ukraine during a period of significant environmental pressure (2016-2024). Our findings demonstrate the severe impact of military operations on Ukraine's forest ecosystems, with total forest losses nearly tripling from 65 thousand hectares in 2021 to 190 thousand hectares by 2024. The methodology utilized Sentinel-1 and Sentinel-2 satellite data processed through the Google Earth Engine platform, demonstrating the effectiveness of cloud-based solutions for large-scale land cover classification in conflict zones.

Our analysis of the Emerald Network reveals concerning patterns of forest destruction in ecologically valuable protected areas, with the most significant losses concentrated in eastern and southern Ukraine. The detailed examination of six critical zones provides assessment of forest ecosystem damage that will be essential for post-war environmental recovery planning.

This research demonstrates the value of remote sensing and machine learning for environmental monitoring in inaccessible or dangerous regions. Future work should focus on developing strategies for forest restoration in damaged areas and continuing to monitor recovery patterns once hostilities cease. These findings contribute vital information for conservation policies and ecological management in Ukraine under challenging circumstances.

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DECLARATION ON GENERATIVE AI

During the preparation of this work the authors used ChatGPT in order to improve language and readability. After using this service, the authors reviewed and edited the content as needed and take full responsibility for the content of the publication.

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